

A review of microbial fuel cells; function, applications, typical design, challenges, and some pathways of development

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ABSTRACT

Microbial Fuel Cells has been known as a promising technology during recent decade for producing sustainable carbon neutral electricity.

Microbial Fuel Cells, abbreviated as MFCs, can be defined as bioreactors that consume organic matter as fuel to produce electrical energy. Generally, MFCs convert chemical energy that is available in the chemical bonds of organic substances to electrical energy. This idea has been around for many decades but is being under scientific evaluation recently due to the energy crisis and warming that the world is facing. The idea seems to be neat and straightforward in the first glance. However, MFCs are not being commercially in application yet due to their low power density level. Regardless, a lot of progress has been made to enhance the performance and efficiency of microbial fuel cells. Researches that have been conducted are from a wide spectrum and have tried to develop the MFC technology in terms of performance, construction cost reduction, and operating costs. In this article, an overview of MFCs, their importance as well as their applications, and how they function will be examined. Then, the challenges towards commercialization of MFCs will be introduced. Last but not least, three specific cases of research that were done recently will be evaluated. The paper tries to address the concepts and reasons behind developments and detailed coverage of designs and improvements requires a larger scope.

INTRODUCTION

As today's world problems, global warming and energy crisis are among the most concerning threats. Gigantic amount of fossil fuel usage and rising greenhouse gas emissions have led minds to start thinking about green technologies and green sources of energy. In this respect, most of the focus has been on different pathways of renewable electricity production. Technologies that emit less to zero carbon are considered as desirable ideals. In this way, Microbial Fuel Cells (MFCs) have provided the idea of electricity generation with zero carbon emission. [1] MFCs are a type of fuel cells that utilize the chemical energy that is available in chemical bonds of waste, organic substance, to generate electricity by using reactions in which

microorganisms play the catalytic role. Therefore, while the main goal of MFCs is to produce electricity, degradation of waste matter or bacteria is achieved during the process. A scheme of a typical MFC is shown in Fig. 1. Like every other fuel cell system, MFC is made of an anode, called anodic chamber and a cathode, called cathodic chamber. In the anodic chamber, electrons are produced via oxidation of organic compounds. Electrons transfer through PEM or salt bridge or nanowires that are produced [2] to the cathode side to form water and carbon dioxide. Despite the fact that carbon dioxide is produced in the cathodic chamber, the net carbon emission of this process is zero because this carbon dioxide is the amount of carbon dioxide that the biomass has taken up to do photosynthesis. The key thing for electric current is to keep the anode side anaerobic. Otherwise, the electrons cannot be extracted in the anode. [1] Moreover, the organic matter has to be oxidized continuously in the anodic chamber. Otherwise, the system is called a biobattery, not a fuel cell. [2] Summing up the explanations above, the reactions that occur in a typical MFC is as follows:

Therefore, water and electricity are produced during the process. Other reactions may occur through the process, but they are not considered as significantly effective in the process.

In the 1980s, scientists figured that electron mediators enhance the power output and current density in great order. Since most of the microbes are not able to completely transmit electrons right to the anode due to the existence of lipid in their outer layer, electron mediators are used. The electron mediators, therefore, are substances that cross through the lipid membrane and set the electrons free to join the anode. Thus, mediators should have specific characters, most important of which are the ability to diffuse through the lipid layer, the ability to take the electrons and carry them to the anode, etc. Some microbes, however, are able to transfer their electrons without the intervention of mediator. These microbes create a biofilm layer on the anode surface and "introduce" the anode as their final electron acceptor. When this kind of bacteria is used as the feed of the system, the system is called mediator-less MFC. This type of MFC is generally cheaper than mediator MFCs since there will be no cost for providing the MFC with the mediator. [1]

Figure 1 Diagram of a two chamber microbial fuel cell

APPLICATIONS OF MFCs

- **Electricity**

As mentioned earlier, MFCs utilize chemical energy to produce electricity. The efficiency, however, is theoretically higher than Carnot cycle, because no heat is generated in the process like other types of fuel cells. According to researches done by Chaudhury and Lovley, Rabaey et al, and Rosenbaum, high amounts of 80%, 89%, and 97% were achieved for electron yield, electron recovery, and columbic efficiency, respectively. Nevertheless, what is most important is power generation, which is still very low. Power generation is the rate of electron extraction from the fuel (organic matter). Ieropoulos et al suggested to store the produced electricity in rechargeable devices, such as capacitors and then discharge the electricity to users. They have also found that MFCs are well-suited for low power applications, such as temperature signal transmission. Wilkinson [4] has found that "Gastrobot, "an intelligent robot that derives all its energy requirements from the digestion of real food" are well-suited to be operated by MFCs. Also, MFCs have the potential to be used in "onboard" applications, such as spaceships. [1]

- **Biohydrogen production**

MFCs are capable of producing hydrogen gas. To form hydrogen, protons and electrons that are released from the anode should meet each other on the cathode side. However, this reaction does not take place by itself because the thermodynamics is not favorable. Thus, an external potential is required to force the reaction to happen. [1] Liu et al have figured that this potential is theoretically equal to 110 mV. Keeping in mind that the amount required for direct electrolysis is 1210 mV and the fact that there will be no need of oxygen in the cathodic chamber, employing MFCs to produce hydrogen is economically feasible. The amount of hydrogen produced is also potentially 8-9 moles per moles of glucose, which is twice as much of the hydrogen that can be produced using fermentation. A researcher named Holzman suggested that hydrogen can also be stored and be used to resolve the problem of MFCs' low power. [1]

- **Wastewater treatment**

As indicated, MFCs produce electricity by oxidizing organic matter. Therefore, they treat waste and can be used for wastewater treatment applications. The fact that electricity is a product of the treatment process results in a considerable decrease in the amount of electricity power required for treatment of wastewater compared to the equivalent amount of wastewater using conventional treatment. [1]

- **MFC as biosensor**

We can potentially use MFCs as biosensors to determine how much BOD change has happened through the treatment process. This can be done by using a correlation between coulombic yield and wastewater strength. [1]

TYPICAL DESIGN OF MFCs

The typical widely-used design for MFCs is a two-chambered design that has the shape of an "H". This design is generally not expensive. A so-called CEM or PEM is used to separate anode from the cathode. Therefore, the material that is used for PEM should have the ability to pass proton across itself. Nafion, Ultrex, and plain salt bridge are among the popular materials used as PEM. Plain salt bridge, however, is the cheapest option, though it results in MFC's low power output due to its high ohmic resistance. The cathode and anode electrodes have to be put in salt and agar solution. Ferricyanide can be employed in the cathodic chamber as the final electron acceptor to enhance power density. Nevertheless, using Ferricyanide has not been approved as sustainable. [3]

Single chamber, packed bed, up flow, air-cathode, photoheterotrophic are the names of other possible MFC designs.

Figure 2 a) Schematic of H-type MFC design- In the anode side, a gas spurger is used to remove the air and keep the anodic chamber anaerobic. In the cathode side, oxygen is dissolved in the solution to act as electron acceptor. The anodic and cathodic chamber are separated by a cation-exchange membrane, CEM, which transfers protons from anode side to the cathode side. (b) Shows an example of a crafted H-type MFC- Figure derived from [3]

CHALLENGES

Challenges on the way to commercialization are categorized into three main sections: System architecture, materials, and microbiological challenges. The power output of the MFC systems varies inversely with the squared sum of resistance in the system. The recent architecture has tried to approach performing with lower resistance. There are two types of resistance in MFC systems, internal resistance and external resistance. External resistance is fixed and cannot be changed, while internal resistance can vary. Therefore, decreasing internal resistance for the sake of increasing power output is ideal regardless of the costs. For example, by decreasing internal resistance from 19900 Ω to 1290 Ω the power output was increased from 2 mW/m² to

40 mW/m². This change in internal resistance was simply done by replacing a salt bridge with a PEM. One limiting factor for power output (P) is the fact that the solubility of oxygen in water is limited. Since air is bubbled into the system in the cathodic chamber to have oxygen as final electron acceptor, low solubility of oxygen in water constrains the concentration of readily available oxygen near the surface of the cathode electrode. P is a function of Open-Circuit Voltage, OCV that is a function of individual potentials of anode and cathode itself. As the anode potential depends on respiratory enzymes and is usually equal to -300 mV, it does not vary significantly in different designs. The cathodic potential, however, varies with oxidant and catholyte. For example, using Ferricyanide as the final electron acceptor increases the cathode potential from 200-300 mV to 361 mV compared with the time that oxygen was used in the cathode side. The cathode potential is equal to 470 mV when using MnO₂, although neither Ferricyanide nor MnO₂ was found sustainable. Hence, considering the fact that the system has to be capable of allowing continuous flow through itself, the cathode can be put in direct contact with air to form a so-called air-cathode MFC, which operates with a significantly higher performance. A power output of 1540 W/m² was achieved using an air-cathode MFC. Another factor that can alter the internal resistance is electrode spacing. By decreasing the electrode spacing from 4 cm to 2 cm, P was increased from 720 mW/m² to 1210 mW/m². [3]

Materials

The most controversial issue with MFCs' materials construction is cost, especially when large scales are under investigation. Possible choices for electrodes' materials range from "carbon cloth and paper to graphite rods, plates, granules, and RCV." Large surface areas are ideal besides the structural strength because they have to be able to support the so called biofilm that is formed on the surface as well as the ability to tolerate the weight of the biofilm. The anode and cathode electrode material can be the same or different. However, the only consideration is that catalyst should be used on the surface of the cathode electrode when oxygen is used as the final electron acceptor. The cathode does not require to have catalyst when ferricyanide or MnO₂ is used as the final electron acceptor. [3]

To summarize, the materials that are used have to have enough structural strength and reasonable cost. If these requirements were fulfilled, the effort should be then focused on using materials that have lowest possible ohmic resistance. This subject will be discussed in the next section.

Microbiology

Many types of microorganisms are able to transfer the electrons that were obtained from the oxidation of the organic matter to the anode. Marine sediment, activated sludge, wastewater, and soil can be introduced as rich sources of these microorganisms. [1] If the bacteria ability to transfer electrons in an exocellular manner, it is called exoelectron. Although the understanding

of electrochemically active bacteria is still very limited, initial comprehension of electron transfer by metal-reducing bacteria such as *Geobacter* and *Shewanella* have been found thanks to research done by Kim et al. It has been observed that some bacteria generate “soluble electron shuttles”. When these shuttles are produced in the system, there will be no need of direct contact of cell and the final electron acceptor. Despite the fact that MFCs have been operated successfully with different bacteria, certain substrates reduce power production. Therefore, the challenge is to recognize a set of bacteria that are able to whether enhance substrates degradation rates, have more efficient electron transfer mechanisms, or to increase the electrical conduction of the biofilm to maintain operating in high current densities. [3]

VOLTAGE GENERATION OF MFC AND LOSSES

The maximum theoretical amount of voltage for an MFC is around 1.1 V. However, due to several losses the achieved open-circuit voltage is 0.8 Volts. This amount goes even lower, down to 0.62 during current generation. The cell voltage can be simply expressed as

$$E_{cell} = E_{emf} - (\Sigma\eta_{anode} + |\Sigma\eta_{cathode}| + IR_{\Omega})$$

In which R_{Ω} is the total ohmic resistance of the MFC and $\Sigma\eta_{anode} + |\Sigma\eta_{cathode}|$ is the sum of overpotentials in the electrodes. The overpotentials in the electrodes constitute of three main losses: (1) activation losses (2) bacterial metabolic losses (3) mass transport or concentration losses.

Ohmic losses. In general, ohmic losses take place because of the resistance available on the way of flowing ions and electrons in the system. Although ohmic resistance for ions occurs in the electrolyte and occurs in electrodes for electrons, they are both expressed as the total amount of IR_{Ω} , because they both follow ohm's law. The ohmic losses can be reduced by using materials of low resistivity. Moreover, reducing electrode spacing and increasing solution conductivity can decrease ohmic losses. It should be noted that the solution conductivity cannot exceed a certain amount due to limited bacteria tolerance. [1]

Activation losses. Activation polarization due to the energy that is required to overcome energy barrier of the chemical reaction of species. Activation losses rise smoothly at high current densities and sharply at low current densities. Thus, activation polarization contributes to most of the voltage loss at low currents. By enhancing the electrode surface activation losses can be decreased. Also, usage of better catalysis and increase in system temperature will decrease the activation polarization because they ease the reaction kinetics. [3]

Bacterial metabolic losses. Bacteria require energy to transfer electrons from a substrate to the final electron acceptor, which can be a compound in the cathode or the anode electrode. Thus, as this transfer starts from a substrate which has a relatively low potential and ends in a high potential, metabolic energy is generated. [1] The more the difference of start and end

potentials, the higher the metabolic energy required and as a result the higher the voltage loss due to bacterial activities. So, the effort here is to maintain the potential of the anode (electron final acceptor) as low as possible, down to a level that does not prevent electron transport, to maximize the MFC voltage. [3]

Concentration losses. Concentration losses occur due to the limitations in mass transfer and diffusion of chemical species to the electrode surface. Concentration losses mostly occur at high current densities. In the anode side, either low discharge rate of the oxidized species from the electrode surface or the low rate of reduced species to the electrode surface cause the concentration loss. The overpotential at the cathode is due to the low amount of dissolved oxygen in the solution. [1] Stirring and bubbling are the two options that can make a well-mixed solution and reduce the concentration gradient and therefore concentration losses at the cathode side. Nevertheless, both operations require energy input, which has to be considered in the study of the balance between power output and the energy consumed by MFC. [3]

In a nutshell, Fig 4 illustrates the place where each of the losses occurs.

Figure 3 Overpotentials through an MFC system 1. Activation losses in the anode side and mass transport losses 2.Bacteria metabolic losses 3. Anodic ohmic losses 4. External resistance that causes voltage drop 5. Ohmic losses in

the membrane 6. Cathodic ohmic losses 7. Activation and mass transport losses from reduction of oxygen. Derived from Rabaey and Verstraet [5]

OVERVIEW OF THREE CASES OF RECENT STUDIES

In this section, the aim is to address the results of three research studies that were done to investigate the feasibility of MFC application in terms of different aspects. The first case is a study on using MFC to treat beer brewery disposal. The second case is a technical and cultural study on using household MFC. The third case is the most recent and promising development in the field of MFC technology.

1. Evaluation of beer brewery wastewater as MFC fuel

This study was done evaluate the feasibility of using MFC system for beer brewery wastewater treatment in China using a single chamber MFC. Accordingly, brewery wastewater was proposed to be a suitable fuel for MFC as it has a relatively high BOD and is not toxic. Also, it contains high amounts of carbohydrate and low ammonium-nitrogen. Therefore, the research aims to investigate the possibility of electricity generation using beer brewery wastewater and compare the results with an identical MFC which consumes domestic wastewater as fuel, and to demonstrate the effect of temperature on power output and COD removal. In this respect, two identical single chamber MFCs were designed and crafted and were used to treat beer brewery wastewater and domestic wastewater. One of the reactors was set to operate at 20°C and the other one at 30°C. The characteristics of the beer brewery wastewater are shown in Table 1. [8]

Parameter	Value
pH	6.5 ± 0.2
COD, mg/L	2250 ± 418
BOD, mg/L	1340 ± 335
TOC, mg/L	970 ± 156
NH ₃ N, mg/L	54 ± 14
Phosphate, mg/L	50 ± 35
Total suspended solids, mg/L	480 ± 70

Table 1 Characteristics of raw beer brewery wastewater

The results demonstrate that by using beer brewery wastewater a more stable voltage was attained compared with domestic wastewater. Moreover, as can be seen in Fig 4, the MFC that

was operating in 30°C yielded a higher voltage of 335 mV than the MFC operating 20°C, which produced 308 mV. [8]

Figure 4 Electricity generation by MFCs, (A) system during using domestic wastewater (B) system with beer brewery wastewater

The system that was operating at 30°C was capable of generating 11.5% more than the one which was operating at 20°C. As can be seen in Fig. 5, by decreasing operating temperature from 30°C to 20°C, both anode and cathode experienced a decrease in their potentials. However, in current densities higher than 2.5 A/m², anode potentials become equal. Also, the impact of temperature was greater on the cathode potential compared with the anode potential. [8]

Figure 5 Anode and cathode potentials at 20°C and 30°C

The power densities of 483 mW/m², 12 W/m³ and 435 mW/m², 11 W/m³ were obtained for the MFCs operating in 30°C and 20°C, respectively. Nevertheless, since the difference is relatively to

a great degree, we can propose that the system is also suitable for cold areas. Fig.6 shows the effect of temperature on power density. [8]

Figure 6 Effect of temperature on power density

2. An example of a novel pilot-scale stacked MFC

Wu et al published the results of their research recently and they have achieved a promising amount of 50.9 W/m^3 of power output. As indicated earlier, power decreases due to volumetric ohmic resistance and inactive volume. Therefore, the idea of stacking small cells together instead of increasing the size of a single cell seems to be a promising idea to enhance the performance of MFCs. The researches that were done so far could not achieve a satisfactory power output. Previous work attained 5.6 W/m^3 for a 1-liter MFC, 11 W/m^3 for a 20-liter MFC and 0.47 W/m^3 for a 250-liter MFC. In this research, however, the researchers crafted a 72-liter stack. Three main hypothesis were applied in their design. 1. The stack should have higher ion exchange membrane areas per volume to ease ion transport. Therefore, the electrode chambers were designed as narrow and flat as possible to reduce distance and resistance. 2. To provide more active area granular activated carbon was employed that enhances the attachment of biofilm to the anode. 3. In order to enhance bioactivity in the anode biofilm and reduce mass transfer resistance, the adsorptive effect of GAC was "pre-verified". Two operation modes of fed-batch and continuous were observed. A maximum power density of 50.9 W/m^3 in fed-batch mode and maximum power density of 42.1 W/m^3 were obtained in continuous mode. The remarkable improvement in the power density in this study demonstrates that by employing CAC packed bed electrode and this type of stack design can be considered as a feasible application of MFCs. Figure 7 shows a schematic diagram of the design. [7]

Schematic of the 72 L pilot SMFC operated in fed-batch (A) and continuous mode (B) and its equivalent circuit at different external electrical connection (C) (The direction of red arrows in Fig. 1C represented the direction of current flows outside the electrode chambers. Figure derived from [7])

3. Cultural and technical feasibility study of MFC in Tanzania

This study was done in Hanan'g district of Tanzania. The objective was to find out if MFCs can be culturally accepted in the area and technically used as an electric source in the household application. The motivation behind this research was the unavailability of a reliable electricity source in the district. The effort was also made to find a back-up source of electricity for small lights when power outages occur. The MFCs were proposed to use cattle manure as fuel. The interview forms were distributed among residents of the district and the results indicate that most of the people do not have any issue with this type of MFCs. However, safety evaluation was needed to be done as MFCs were going to be used in houses. The household MFCs built in this study were able to operate with manure and an average voltage of 0.08 V was attained. Therefore, the application is constrained in a small scale. Subsidizing MFC costs was suggested as a good option to make usage of MFCs feasible as there are NGOs that are interested to support the green energies' usage. The findings of this study illustrates that further studies are required be done to see if a sustainable MFC power source can be achieved. [6]

CONCLUSIONS

The paper tried to first give the reader an overview of MFCs since the study of MFC technology has not been popular for so long. Then, functionality, challenges, and applications were investigated. After that, generated voltage and the losses in MFC systems, as well as reasons affecting losses, and therefore voltage were evaluated mostly in a qualitative way. In the last part of the paper, three different studies that were interesting in terms of fuel compatibility, technical and cultural feasibility, and design development were introduced to give the reader a sense of how broad is the spectra of possible developments in MFC technology that has to be conducted to achieve commercialization.

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